

Review of Fractal and Fractal Derivatives in relation to the Physics of Fractals*

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ABSTRACT

Fractional and fractal derivatives are both generalizations of the usual derivatives that consider derivatives of non-integer orders. Interest in these generalizations has been triggered by a resurgence of clamor to develop a mathematical tool to describe "roughness" in the spirit of Mandelbrot's (1967) Fractal Geometry. Fractional derivatives take the analytic approach towards developing a rational order derivative while fractal derivatives follow a more concrete, albeit geometric approach to the same end. Since both approaches alleged to extend whole derivatives to rational derivatives, it is not surprising that confusion will arise over which generalization to use in practice. This paper attempts to highlight the connection between the various generalizations to fractional and fractal derivatives with the end-in-view of making these concepts useful in various Physics applications and to resolve some of the confusion that arise out of the fundamental philosophical differences in the derivation of fractional derivatives (non-local concept) and fractal derivatives (local concept).

Keywords: *fractional derivative, fractal derivative, fractional differential operators, fractal analysis*

I. NON-INTEGER ORDER OF DIFFERENTIATION

L'Hospital (1695) wrote a letter to Leibnitz raising the possibility of a half derivative of the function $f(x) = x$ to which the latter responded that "this could lead to a paradox for which the consequences may be useful in the future". Leibnitz realized *ab initio* that there are various ways of generalizing the discrete operation of

differentiation to the continuous case which lead to non-equivalent results. To date, there are two (2) main streams of generalizations pursued by researchers: the purely analytical stream (Fractional Calculus) and the physical-geometric stream (Fractal Calculus) (West, Bologna & Grigolini, 2003; Miller & Ross, 1993; Hilfer, 2000). To illustrate the differences in results for the two

approaches. the half derivative of $f(x) = x$ are:

1. $\frac{d^{\frac{1}{2}}f(x)}{dx^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{2\sqrt{x}}{\sqrt{\pi}}$ (fractional derivative)
2. $\frac{df(x)}{dx^{\frac{1}{2}}} = 2\sqrt{x}$ (fractal derivative with scaled x)
3. $\frac{df^{\frac{1}{2}}}{dx^{\frac{1}{2}}} = 1$ (fractal derivative with both variables scaled)

The half fractional derivative of $f(x)$ does not represent a local operation i.e. it does not represent “slope” at a point, but differentiation over a range of values of x . On the other hand, the half fractal derivative of the same function re-scales either the independent variable $\frac{df(x)}{dx^{\frac{1}{2}}}$ or both $(\frac{df^{\frac{1}{2}}}{dx^{\frac{1}{2}}})$ and applies the usual differentiation on the re-scaled values. The latter approach is greatly influenced by the work of Mandelbrot (1967) in Fractal Geometry where description of the “roughness” of physical objects is the main focus.

Recent developments in Fractional Calculus have demonstrated the intrinsic mathematical elegance of a purely analytic approach. For instance, the generalized differential operator defined by:

$$4. D^n[f(x)] = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{(1-B_\varepsilon)^n}{\varepsilon^n} \right) f(x)$$

where $B_\varepsilon f(x) = f(x - \varepsilon)$, yields the usual differentiation for $n = 1$ and the usual integration for $n = -1$. Such elegant results pave the way for a re-examination of the various concepts in classical Calculus viz. the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus. Meanwhile, developments in Fractal Calculus have demonstrated a strong inclination toward practical applications of the concept of a real order derivatives in physics and the physical sciences. Chen et al. (2003) used Fractal Calculus in investigating anomalous diffusion; Pant et al. (2012) considered Fractal Calculus in the study of diffusivity in porous media; Danijela et al. (2013)

investigated Columbeau-generated stochastic processes through fractal derivatives.

In a 2012 paper, Xiao-Jun Yang (2012) used the term Local Fractional Calculus (LFC) to denote Fractal Calculus for the development of a Local Fractional Fourier Analysis. He defines local fractional calculus as “dealing with everywhere continuous but nowhere differentiable functions in fractal spaces”. We note that Yang’s paper highlights the key difference between Fractional Calculus, on one hand, and Fractal Calculus on the other. The former is a non-local concept while the latter is a local one. In Fractional Calculus, we speak of differentiation over a range of values of x while in Fractal Calculus, we deal with differentiation at a point x .

As a relatively young field of inquiry, there is bound to be a lot of confusion over the concepts of “fractional” and “fractal” derivatives because both deal with non-integer derivatives. The first concept is a purely analytic one while the latter has a strong geometric flavor. In fact, we propose to use the term “scaled calculus” for fractal calculus in order to reduce confusion with fractional calculus. The paper is organized as follows: Sections II and III deal with the development of fractional derivatives; Section IV derives fractal derivatives; Section V concludes with a series of simple applications of fractal calculus in Physics. With this paper, it is hoped that: (1) the differences, both in philosophy and use, of fractional and fractal derivatives are clarified, and (2) research interest in both developments will be further stimulated.

II. GENERALIZATION TO FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES BASED ON EXPONENTIAL AND POLYNOMIAL FUNCTIONS

Consider the exponential function:

$$1. f(x) = e^{ax}$$

whose k th derivative is:

$$2. \frac{d^k}{dx^k} e^{ax} = a^k e^{ax}.$$

A natural way to generalize to rational derivatives is to set $k = q \in \mathbb{R}^+$ to yield:

$$3. \frac{d^q}{dx^q} e^{ax} = a^q e^{ax}.$$

Any function that can be expressed as a linear sum of exponential functions can be differentiated in rational orders. In particular, since:

$$4. \cos(x) = \frac{e^{ix} + e^{-ix}}{2}$$

It follows that:

$$5. \frac{d^q}{dx^q} (\cos(x)) = \cos(x + \frac{\pi}{2} q).$$

The last result indicates that the fractional differential operator shifts the phase of the trigonometric function in fractional proportion. The same statement can be said of the sine function. The approach using exponential functions as a way to generalize fractional derivatives appears to be satisfactory yet, L'Hospital wanted the "half derivative" of $f(x) = x$. There is no apparent representation of $f(x)$ as an exponential function taking the form of (1). Note that $f(x) = e^{\log(x)}$ is not the same as (1). The other way is to find the Fourier representation of the function (which is not defined over the entire interval) over some finite interval. However, ambiguities cannot be avoided here because of the choice of the finite interval. In other words, the fractional derivative obtained in this manner is neither unique nor local (i.e. whole derivatives are both unique and local).

Instead of beginning with an exponential function, we can attempt to build fractional derivatives by considering the polynomial function:

$$6. f(x) = x^m$$

whose k th derivative is :

$$7. \frac{d^k}{dx^k} x^m = m(m-1)(m-2) \dots (m-k+1)x^{m-k}$$

The Gamma function or generalized factorial can be used to make the result above applicable to any positive rational order of derivative. The Gamma function is :

$$8. \Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty x^{\alpha-1} e^{-x} dx = (\alpha-1)\Gamma(\alpha-1),$$

which allows us to write (7) as:

$$9. \frac{d^k}{dx^k} x^m = \frac{\Gamma(m+1)}{\Gamma(m+1-k)} x^{m-k}$$

with the recurrence relation $\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!$ and the reflection relation $\Gamma(x)\Gamma(1-x) = \frac{\pi}{\sin \pi x}$

Replacing k with $q \in \mathbb{Q}_+$, we obtain the desired generalization. In response to Leibnitz, the half derivative of x now becomes:

$$10. \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}} (x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} x^{1/2}$$

$$\text{since } \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$$

While we are used to thinking of the derivative of a constant to be equal to zero, the half-derivative of a constant is not zero but:

$$11. \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}} (c) = \frac{c}{\Gamma(1/2)} x^{-1/2} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\pi x}}, \quad \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}$$

which is not defined at $x = 0$.

We point out that combining the two approaches lead to some curious results. For instance, we know that:

$$12. e^x = \sum_0^\infty \frac{x^n}{n!}$$

but

$$13. \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}} e^x = (1)^{1/2} e^x = e^x$$

$$\frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}} e^x = \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}} \sum_0^\infty \frac{x^n}{n!} = \sum_0^\infty \frac{\Gamma(n+1)x^{n-1/2}}{\Gamma(n+\frac{1}{2})} \neq e^x$$

Results such as (13) are not rare and for which reason, Leibnitz was right in pointing out that generalization to rational order derivatives indeed lead to paradoxes.

III. GENERALIZATION TO FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES BASED ON A LIMIT DEFINITION

We next examine yet another approach that is more basic than the derivations of fractional derivatives based on the exponential and polynomial functions. The definition of a positive integer derivative is based on:

$$14. \frac{d}{dx} (f(x)) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x) - f(x-\epsilon)}{\epsilon}$$

which can be repeated n times to yield:

$$\frac{d^n}{dx^n} (f(x)) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\epsilon^n} \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j nC_j f(x - j\epsilon)$$

where nC_j is the number of combinations of n objects taken j at a time. In order to generalize this formula when n is not a positive integer, we need to generalize in two directions: the binomial coefficients and the upper limit of the summation.

Consider a function f(x) shown below :

Figure 1. Function f(x)

Given $\epsilon > 0$, we move five equi-steps to the left to obtain the points $x - 5\epsilon, x - 4\epsilon, \dots, x - \epsilon$. In general, let k be the number of such points, then $x = k\epsilon$. Define the ϵ - backward shift operator as: $B_\epsilon(f(x)) = f(x-\epsilon)$. The general differential operator D is defined by:

$$16. D^n [f(x)] = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{(1-B_\epsilon)^n}{\epsilon^n} \right) f(x)$$

For $n = 1$, we obtain the usual differential operator:

$$17. D(f(x)) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x) - f(x-\epsilon)}{\epsilon}$$

while for $n = -1$, we make use of the geometric series representation:

$$18. \frac{\epsilon}{(1-B_\epsilon)} = \epsilon [1 + B_\epsilon + \dots + B_\epsilon^k + \dots]$$

This gives:

$$19. D^{-1}[f(x)] = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{(1-B_\epsilon)^{-1}}{\epsilon^{-1}} \right) f(x) = \epsilon [f(x) + f(x-\epsilon) + f(x-2\epsilon) + \dots + f(x-k\epsilon) + \dots]$$

Equation (16) gives the differential operator while (19) yields the integration operator in the limit as ϵ tends to zero. An algebraic expression for the Fundamental Theorem in Calculus can be obtained from (19) and (9) namely, that:

“If $\frac{d^k}{dx^k} x^m = \frac{\Gamma(m+1)}{\Gamma(m+1-k)} x^{m-k} = D^k x^m$, then for $k=-1, D^{-1}(x^m)$ is the integral of $x^{m''}$ ”

For example, if $f(x) = x^2$, then $D^{-1}(x^2) = \frac{2!}{\Gamma(2+1-(-1))} x^{2-(-1)} = \frac{2!}{3!} x^3 = \frac{1}{3} x^3$.

The upper limit of the summation in Equation (15) becomes:

$$\frac{d^n}{dx^n} (f(x)) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\epsilon^n} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{x-x_0}{\epsilon} \rfloor} (-1)^j nC_j f(x - j\epsilon)$$

where x_0 is usually zero, or $\Gamma[\frac{x}{2}]$

We then proceed to define the binomial coefficients in a way that does not require integer values of n. Note that:

$$nC_j = \frac{n!}{j!(n-j)!}$$

which suggests that an alternative way of writing factorials for non-integer arguments be used. This

is facilitated by using the Gamma function (8). Doing so, we obtain:

$$\frac{d^q}{dx^q}(f(x)) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^q} \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{x-x_0}{\varepsilon}} (-1)^j \frac{\Gamma(q+1)}{j! \Gamma(q+1-j)} f(x-j\varepsilon)$$

The general derivative depends on the value of the function f over the range from x_0 to x and is therefore a non-local operation. We can see this from the fact that in the factor $f(x-j\varepsilon)$ in the summation, the argument ranges from x to zero as j ranges from $j = 0$ to $j = \lceil (x - x_0)/\varepsilon \rceil$.

Using (20), L'Hospital's query to Leibnitz yields:

$$21. \quad \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} x^{1/2}$$

which is identical with (8).

We therefore see that the generalized derivative obtained by the polynomial approach and that which is obtained by the limit approach give identical results. The utility of using the generalized limit approach over the polynomial approach is that the generalized limit approach allows us to find rational order derivatives even if the function is not expressible as a power series. Moreover, the polynomial approach does not give us any indication about the non-locality of the generalized derivative, that is, the dependence on the function over a range rather than on just a single point.

IV. RECONCILING THE EXPONENTIAL APPROACH AND THE GENERALIZED LIMIT APPROACH TO FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES

In Section II, we pointed out the conflicting results when we took the half-derivative of e^x using the exponential approach and the polynomial approach (or the generalized limit approach). The derivative of this function (including half derivatives) should yield the same function. Moreover, the function approaches 1 as x tends to zero. Yet, the half derivative of e^x is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^{1/2}}{dx^{1/2}}(f(x)) &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{1/2}} \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{x-x_0}{\varepsilon}} (-1)^j \frac{\Gamma(3/2)}{j! \Gamma(3/2-j)} f(x-j\varepsilon) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi x}} \left(1 + 2x + \frac{4}{3} x^2 + \frac{8}{15} x^3 + \frac{16}{105} x^4 + \dots \right) \end{aligned}$$

which goes to infinity as x goes to zero. How can we reconcile the two results? The answer lies on the fact that half-derivatives depend on the chosen range of differentiation. For instance,

$$\int_{x_0}^x e^x = e^x - e^{x_0}$$

and the only way for the derivative of the right-hand side to equal to the argument of the definite integral on the left-hand side is when $x_0 = -\infty$ which we have assumed tacitly. In other words, ranges of differentiation are important when we talk of fractional derivatives (derivatives over a range of values rather than derivative at a single point). If $x_0 = -\infty$, then we find that the upper limit of (22) simply becomes ∞ and hence, the half-derivative in (21) becomes e^x also.

V. FRACTAL DIMENSIONS, ROUGHNESS, FRACTAL CALCULUS AND FRACTIONAL CALCULUS

The motivation for developing Fractional Calculus stemmed from a purely analytic question of L'Hospital (1695). Recent interest in fractal geometry and analysis, however, spawned yet another direction for generalizing the usual derivative. This direction is towards defining **Fractal Derivatives** as basis for describing data and geometric roughness. As such, we expect a relationship between fractal derivatives and fractal dimensions. What is not clear yet is the relationship between fractal derivatives and fractional derivatives.

Fractal Derivative

Let $f(t)$ be a function. We define the q^{th} fractal derivative of $f(t)$ with respect to a fractal measure t as:

$$(23) \quad \frac{d f(t)}{dt^q} = \lim_{t_1 \rightarrow t} \frac{f(t_1) - f(t)}{t_1^q - t^q}, \quad q > 0$$

Note at once that while for fractional derivatives $\varepsilon = |t - t_1|$ for fractal derivatives we have $\varepsilon^q = |t_1^q - t^q|$. This implies that

$$(24) \quad \frac{d f(t)}{d t^q} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(t_2) - f(t_1^q - \varepsilon^q)^{1/q}}{\varepsilon^q}$$

Comparing (24) and (20), we see that (24) cannot be expressed in terms of simple backshift operators. In particular, the half - derivative of $f(t) = t$ becomes:

$$(25) \quad \frac{d f(t)}{d t^{\frac{1}{2}}} = 2\sqrt{t}$$

which differs from (21) by a factor of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}}$. A more general representation of a fractal derivative with respect to both f(t) and t is:

$$(26) \quad \frac{d f^r}{d t^q} = \lim_{t_2 \rightarrow t} \frac{f^r(t_2) - f^r(t)}{t_2^q - t^q}, \quad r, q > 0.$$

Hence for f(t) = t with $r = q = \frac{1}{2}$:

$$(27) \quad \frac{d f^{1/2}}{d t^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \lim_{t_2 \rightarrow t} \frac{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t}}{t_2^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} = 1$$

which coincides with $\frac{d f}{d t} = 1$.

Observations:

- a) The fractal derivative $\frac{d f}{d t^q}$ is always a function of the fractional derivative $\frac{d^q f}{d t^q}$.
- b) To avoid confusion, we change notation for fractal derivatives. Instead of writing $\frac{d f^r}{d t^q}$, we write $G(r, q)$ for Equation (26). Likewise, instead of writing $\frac{d^q f(t)}{d t^q}$ for the qth fractional derivative, we write A(q). The $G(., .)$ notation reflects the **geometric nature** of (26) while the $A(.)$ notation highlights the **analytic feature** of the fractional derivative Equation (20)
- c) Statement (a) can be written as:

$$A(q) = T(G(0, q)),$$

where T(.) is a functional of $G(., .)$.

We can compare the fractal derivative $G(0, \frac{1}{2})$ of $f(t) = e^t$ with its corresponding fractional derivative $A(\frac{1}{2})$. For reference, we reproduce (22) below:

$$A\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)[e^t] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(t^{-\frac{1}{2}} + 2t^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{3}{4}t^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{8}{15}t^{\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{16}{105}t^{\frac{7}{2}} \dots \right)$$

→ *Fractional Derivative*

The corresponding fractal derivative is:

$$G\left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right)[e^t] = 2t^{\frac{1}{2}} + 2t^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{3}{2}t^{\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{8}{5}t^{\frac{7}{2}} \dots \rightarrow \text{Fractal Derivative}$$

For $t > 0$, the fractal derivative is generally greater than the fractional derivative. As $t > 0$, the fractional derivative tends to infinity while the fractal derivative tends to zero; both behaviors being inconsistent with the fractional derivative of e^t using the exponential approach viz. $f^{\frac{1}{2}}(e^t) = (1)^{\frac{1}{2}}e^t = e^t \rightarrow 1$ as $t \rightarrow 0$. The behaviors of the derivatives $A(\frac{1}{2})$, $G(0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $f^t(t)$ of e^t are shown below

Figure 2. e^t

Figure 3. half fractal derivative

Figure 4. half fractional derivative

0 < t < .51

t	exp(t)	A(1/2)	G(0,1/2)
0.00169	1.0017	13.77046	0.082358
0.00622	1.0062	7.242892	0.158716
0.00636	1.0064	7.164721	0.160515
0.02289	1.0232	3.901294	0.309542
0.0237	1.024	3.84009	0.315223
0.02547	1.0258	3.717008	0.327352
0.02599	1.0263	3.683348	0.330845
0.02788	1.0283	3.569347	0.343301
0.03151	1.032	3.381066	0.366268
0.50395	1.6552	1.80922	2.225664

1 < t < 1.036

t	exp(t)	A(1/2)	G(0,1/2)
1.00019	2.7188	2.502952	4.66774
1.00045	2.7195	2.503464	4.6693
1.00645	2.7359	2.515332	4.705406
1.01012	2.7459	2.522633	4.727583
1.01249	2.7524	2.527365	4.741942
1.01273	2.7531	2.527845	4.743398
1.01772	2.7669	2.537853	4.773732
1.02446	2.7856	2.551465	4.814913
1.02761	2.7944	2.557863	4.834241
1.03589	2.8176	2.574793	4.885299

1.5 < t < 1.55

T	exp(t)	A(1/2)	G(0,1/2)
1.50904	4.5224	3.83446	8.503707
1.5178	4.5622	3.863687	8.585542
1.51835	4.5647	3.86553	8.590701
1.51986	4.5716	3.870594	8.604875
1.52179	4.5804	3.877077	8.623018
1.52312	4.5865	3.881551	8.635538
1.52507	4.5955	3.88812	8.653921
1.52573	4.5985	3.890347	8.660149
1.52706	4.6046	3.894837	8.672711
1.53064	4.6211	3.90695	8.706595

2 < t < 2.05

t	exp(t)	A(1/2)	G(0,1/2)
2.00068	7.3941	5.86979	14.15103
2.01024	7.4651	5.918051	14.28454
2.01281	7.4843	5.931086	14.3206
2.0134	7.4887	5.934082	14.32889
2.01531	7.503	5.943791	14.35575
2.03163	7.6265	6.02734	14.58689
2.03406	7.6451	6.03987	14.62156
2.03733	7.6701	6.05677	14.66831
2.04045	7.6941	6.072934	14.71304
2.04153	7.7024	6.078538	14.72854

In the neighborhood of zero, the analytic fractional derivative is larger than the geometric fractal derivative. As we move away from zero (somewhere near $t = 0.50$), the geometric fractal derivative dominates both the analytic fractional derivative and the fractional derivative obtained through the exponential approach. There appears to be some simple relationship that governs the behavior of the exponential fractional derivative (e^t) and the geometric fractal derivative. We performed a regression analysis using $y = e^t$ and $x = G(0,1/2)$. The results are shown below:

Figure 5. Graph of $x = G(0,1/2)$ versus $y = \exp(t)$

The regression equation is $\exp(t) = 0.198 + 0.539 G(0,1/2)$

Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	T	P
Constant	0.19798	0.01841	10.75	0.000
$G(0,1/2)$	0.539015	0.001241	434.33	0.000
S = 0.3696 R-Sq = 99.5% R-Sq(adj) = 99.5%				

That is, the exponential fractional derivative is about one-half of the geometric fractal derivative. The two plots of the other possible relationships between the three half-derivatives are shown below:

Figure 6. Plot of $x = A(1/2)$ and $y = \exp(t)$

Figure 7. Plot of $x = A(1/2)$ and $y = G(0,1/2)$

Note that Figures 5 and 6 are almost identical. This observation simply comes from the fact that the geometric fractal derivative ($G(0,1/2)$) and the fractional derivative obtained by the exponential approach (e^t) are linearly related.

VI. SOME APPLICATION OF FRACTAL DERIVATIVES

Physical laws of diffusion that are based on a Euclidean medium cannot apply if in fact the media exhibit fractal properties. Some physical realizations of fractal media include water turbulence porous media and aquifers. In the latter case, the physical concepts of space and time have to be rescaled to, (x^r, t^q) where r, q are positive real numbers, in order to conform to the fractal nature of space-time. In this fractal space-time system, the notion of a velocity can be redefined as:

$$28. G(r, q)S(x, t) = \frac{dx^r}{dt^q}$$

because the traditional definition of velocity is meaningless in a non-differentiable fractal space-time.

Fractal Linear Motion

Linear motions involving the concepts of velocity and acceleration are fundamental in Physics. The usual distance traversed by a free-falling body after time t is:

$$29. x(t) = \frac{1}{2}gt^2$$

where g is assumed constant. Suppose that the space $x(t)$ is fractal of dimension r , then the velocity of the body at any constant t , becomes

$$30. \frac{d(x^r)}{dt} = \lim_{t \rightarrow t_1} \frac{\frac{1}{2}gt^{2r} - (\frac{1}{2}gt_1^2)^r}{t - t_1}$$

$$= \frac{-r}{2^{r-1}} g^r t_1^{2r-1}$$

Note that if the fractal dimension of $x(t)$ is $r = 1$, we obtain the usual velocity as:

$$v = -gt.$$

However, if $x(t)$ is fragmented with, say, $r = 0.63$, the velocity is:

$$v^{0.63} = -(2^{0.37} x(0.63) g^{0.63} t_1^{0.26})$$

which is slower than gt , as one would expect if one were travelling along a rough media e.g variable air resistance.

Fick's Second Law Anomalous Motion

Consider the anomalous transport-diffusion process which is an alternative to Fick's Second Law given by:

$$32. \frac{d^2 u(x,t)}{dt^q} = D \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^r} \left(\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x^r} \right) \right), -\infty < x < \infty, u(x, 0) = \delta(x)$$

where $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta function, and $0 < q < 2$, $0 < r < 1$. The fundamental solution to (32) can be obtained by the transformation $t^* = t^q$ and $x^* = x^r$ which transform (32) into the usual diffusion equation. The solution, of course, is given by:

$$33. u(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi t^q}} \exp\left(\frac{-x^{2r}}{4t^q}\right)$$

which is the stretched normal (Gaussian) distribution. From this example, we learn that in order to deal with fractal space-time, it is necessary to know the fractal dimensions r and q of the space (x) and the time (t) respectively. The corresponding fractal derivatives can be calculated and the solution to a fractal differential

equation obtained by transformation of variables.

Fourier's Law of Heat Conduction

As a third example, consider Fourier's law (1822) (see Fourier, 1955) which states that "thermal conduction results into heat flux which is proportional to the magnitude of the temperature gradient and opposite to it in sign". Thus, for a one-direction conduction process, this can be translated to:

$$31. h_x = -c \frac{dT}{dx}$$

where c is the thermal conductivity constant, h_x is the heat flux in W/m^2 in the positive x direction and dT/dx is the (negative) temperature gradient (K/m) in the direction of the heat flow (usually, from hot to cold regions). Suppose now that the space (x) is fractal of dimension r while T is of fractal dimension q , then Fourier's law translates to:

$$32. h_x = -c \frac{dT^q}{dx^r}$$

whose solution is obtained by the transformation $x^* = x^r$ and $T^* = T^q$. Equation (35) is the anomalous heat conduction equation.

Other examples may be constructed where the use of fractal derivatives is exemplified. The reader may wish to refer to Darcy's law. Darcy's law relates the instantaneous discharge rate through a porous medium and the viscosity of the fluid with pressure drop over a given distance.

VII CONCLUSION

While we have found a linear relationship between fractal derivatives ($G(0,q)$) and fractional derivatives through the exponential definition, much is still to be done in terms of relating analytic fractional derivatives ($A(q)$) and fractal derivatives ($G(0,q)$). A relationship between $A(q)$ and $G(0,q)$, if found, would be useful in terms of developing an entire theory of fractal calculus (as opposed to fractional calculus). A fractal calculus theory would, in turn, be useful in re-analyzing most of the laws in Physics e.g. quantum theory.

The key to such an examination lies on the premise of a local versus non-local derivatives.

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